

THE ADEQUACY OF TRANSLATION OF MATH TERMS INTO UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Raximova Dildora Kobiljonovna

Senior Lecturer of TMC Institute

Abstract

In general, fairy-tales include a number of notions which help children get mathematical notions about the surrounding world, its variety and glory. Fairy-tales not only develop children's imagination but also develop their skills to use mathematical connections and basic notions in a simple understandable language in primary and preschools mathematics education, at the same time putting

stress on these connections and so paving the way to further serious acquisition of the systemic course of mathematics. It is advisable to use fairy – tales for the development of the learner's comprehension of mathematical notions.

Keywords

neutrality, reality, generalization, concretization, dialects, Avoirdupois, feet, ounce, Fahrenheit, pint

Each educational sphere has its own field of study and set of problematic issues.

Similarly, there are a number of translation problems, and they are considered as pragmatic translation problems. The pragmatic problems of translation have not yet been studied in depth and are still being studied. There are many pragmatic problems in translation, which can include: adequacy, genre characteristics of the original and background knowledge of the intended reader, communicative purpose, pragmatic neutrality, reality, generalization, concretization, dialects, modernization of the original, and a number of similar issues. One of the main problems of translation is pragmatic adequacy. Adequate translation is the complete translation.¹⁹³

The authors of the concept of adequate translation are AV Fedorov and Ya. I. Resker urges not to think of translation as a clear narrative.

Both translation and narration are in accordance with the norms and rules of the translated language, if they are done at a high level. According to A.V.

¹⁹³ Newmark, P. (1988b). *Approaches to Translation*. Hertfordshire: Prentice Hall.

Fedorov and Ya. I. Resker, a complete translation is an adequate translation that fully reflects the original, corresponds to it and equates with it.

As an example from the passage ;

“Just then, the goose soared about 29,000 **feet**”.

O'sha damda, g'oz taxminan 29,000 fut balandlikka ko'tarildi .

In Uzbek translation , if the word "balandlik" is not included after the term “**feet**”, as a result this word becomes incomprehensible to the Uzbek reader.

As we can see that the more familiar the term "feet" is in the dictionary of America, Great Britain and other countries ,the more unfamiliar , challenging incomprehensible for the Uzbek reader as well. The reason is that , such unit of measurement (pl **feet** symbol, **ft**) , unit of length in the imperial and US customary systems of measurement but it does not exist or is not used in Uzbek system of measurement.

Here we can see another example: “She dumped a **16-ounce** bag of flour into the large mixing bowl”. *U 16 untsiya og'irlikda keladigan unni aralash tirgichga soldi.* If we see the second example the term “**ounce**” which is a unit of mass, weight or volume is used in most British customary system of measurement is given. We know that, there is no such math term in the Uzbek dictionary.

If we translate this term directly from the English language, it causes the reader some misunderstandings. To avoid this, in most cases, concrete meaningful words can also be added to become understandable to everyone in the translation.

Besides, we encounter so many unfamiliar mathematical terms in the children's math based fairy tale books.

For example: “I need 2 **pounds** of overripe bananas”, said the little red hen.

“Menga 2 qadoq yaxshi pishgan bananlar kerak bo'ladi”, dedi qizg'ish tovuq

The purpose of using the term “**qadoq**” is an ancient unit of measurement of weight and is equal to 1 pound; 1Q.=1 pound = 409,512 kg .

This method is called the generalization in translation. Generalization is two side of the same coin: generalization occurs when a word or phrase in the source text is translated into a broader and more general term in the target text, while particularization occurs when a word or phrase in the source text is transferred into a more specific and particular term in the target text.

Thus, we have another example : The temperature was on easy **90 degrees Fahrenheit**.

If we interpret it into Uzbek it sounds like: *Chidab bo'lmas jazirama, dedi, u.* In the following example “**ninety**” indicates temperature, and Fahrenheit shows

90 degrees with the level of heat. But , the definition of Fahrenheit scale is unfamiliar to elementary schoolchildren and if we translate as "the temperature has reached ninety degrees", this may surprise them, because we have been accepted the Celsius system, and the reader can understand the above sentence exactly on the Celsius scale. . In this case, it is necessary to bring the following comment under the page to the translation of the sentence : The **Fahrenheit** is a scale for measuring temperature, in which water freezes at 32 degrees and boils at 212 degrees and it is represented by the symbol °F

Therefore, the method of generalization was used in this passage as well. The need to re-create the translated text in an understandable language to the recipient in order to convey elements that are difficult to understand in the original text and will force to provide additional explanations to the translator . Although such elements are perfectly understandable for the readers of the native language, the translation language may not mean anything to the readers. Thus, the implicit information becomes explicit for the reader in the translated text:

“ She poured in **2 pints** of water“.

Each English person who reads this sentence knows well what pint is (a unit of liquid or dry capacity equal to one eighth of a gallon, in Britain equal to 0.568 litre and in the US equal to 0.473 litre (for liquid measure) or 0.551 litre (for dry measure). But for Uzbek readers, this sentence is unknown, and as a result the translator has to utilize by lexical transformation for changing some lexical units:

“*U idishga 2 pinta miqdorda keladigan suvni soldi.*”

In most cases, such transformations occur in the character of generalization. Generalization is the replacement of concrete meaningful words with common meaningful words that are understandable to everyone in the translation language.

We know that most words in the language have two different meanings—denotative and connotative it means own and portable. If the pragmatic nature of the original text is imposed on such words, then in translation it arises the question to what way to change them . In order to convey the pragmatic nature of the portable words in the text , the translator must be aware of its contextual

meaning , sequence of events in it. After knowing in what way a word in the original text is used, then we choose the corresponding equivalents in the target language.

For instance: “The coach limited his recruiting to linebackers of a certain *avoirdu pois*”

If we interpret it into Uzbek it sounds like:

Murabbiy tarkibga ma'lum miqdordagi himoyachilarni saralash bilan cheklandi.

In particular, unlike the Uzbek interpretation, the original content was much more incomprehensive in that case we used certain method of translation to draw readers attention not to that term maybe its meaning . It is common for the Englishmen **Avoirdupois** is a system of weights based on a pound of 16 ounces or 7,000 grains, widely used in English-speaking countries.

The choice of the necessary meaning and the necessary word ensures communicative completeness of the translation into the original text.

Since no language can cover all aspects of life, a particular notion that expresses a certain language in one language may not have its equivalent in another language or an alternative. In these cases, more is referred to as the turning point of translation practice, that is, word-for-word translation.

In a sense, pragmatic factors are considered a structural element of equivalence, and it creates a communicative completeness of the translation to the original text. As a result, the translation acquires an alternative stylistic feature and is influenced by the level of impression that the reader receives from the reading of the work. The implementation of the pragmatic function of a particular translation requires the translator to give up a high degree of conformity and to prioritize the degree of aesthetic impact of the reader. Because excessive accuracy can lead to pragmatic uncertainty, as a result the translation can weaken the level of impressiveness that the original text has shown to its reader.

In conclusion, the pragmatic adequacy of the translation to the original text is expressed that when the translators and translation have the same information.

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